

Transparent, Referenceable, Integrated, Preservation Planning

TRIPP

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Audience & Scope

This paper is *not* intended for a general audience. Most people with knowledge of repository criteria and practice will be familiar with most of the terms here, or will be able to find them easily from the referenced sources. This text provides a narrative flow to demonstrate the connections between high level activities and functions (FIDELIS project) and detailed core preservation processes (EDEN project). This helps test and validate both outputs and ensures our work is aligned. As current and future EDEN and FIDELIS efforts map this work to other criteria, standards and practices we hope to make the complex digital object management space easier to navigate.

Introduction

This brief working paper proposes that any organisational entity that looks after data and/or metadata should take an approach that integrates retention, curation and preservation planning, and shares a transparent and referenceable (i.e. structured, persistently identified, resolvable) set of supporting information.

The transparent supporting information should be managed in line with metadata schemas, controlled vocabularies and other semantic artefacts, ideally in a machine-actionable way. Where necessary, links to prose information artefacts like policies and procedures should be provided.

The goal is not to normalise or enforce standardised terms, that would create 'yet another' set of criteria. Instead we're using two approaches (that are already mapped to existing criteria) to propose a step forwards in aligning common practice.

We can't detail every source term here, but will clarify where they're from¹ by adding subscripts (CPP, MaDSAF, LoRCAP, LTDR) and underlining Policy Names. The first section below provides an overview of those sources.

The second section provides an overview of *Integrated Preservation Planning* using the terms and policies from the sources. Information artefacts like policies and procedures are a key reference point for information transparency. These artefacts also act as a starting point for identifying where more granular and machine actionable metadata could be applied.

The third section briefly examines the metadata and data services' activities and functions that are not directly aligned with the 'core preservation processes', and considers why.

The overall vision is the eventual provision of a TRIPP template that all repositories can use to share and to clarify their practice.

Referenced Sources Overview

The FIDELIS² TTRAM³ is seeking to develop a matrix of attributes about repositories that should be made transparent to demonstrate trustworthiness. TTRAM uses a list of Activities and Functions (**A|F**) repositories taken from the MaDSAF⁴, which are high-level and intended for mapping across multiple existing criteria. The TTRAM uses levels of retention, curation and preservation (**LoRCAP**⁵) to differentiate types of care offered by repositories.

¹ There may be quite a few footnotes to try and keep the main body of the text flowing.

² FIDELIS Project and Network <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

³ Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144141>

⁴ Metadata and Data Services: Activities-Functions <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779868>

⁵ CoreTrustSeal Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

As identified by the EOSC Long Term Data Retention (**LTDR**) Task Force, the LoRCAP imply different assessment and intervention points in the digital object lifecycle from initial *retention*_{LoRCAP}, through to *reappraisal*_{LTDR}, and potentially to eventual *disposal*_{CPP}.

Diagram 1: Assessment and intervention points with reference to LoRCAP and TTRAM (MaDSAF A|F)

The EDEN⁶ Core Preservation Processes (**CPP**)⁷ focus⁸ on *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}, defining practical, hand-on operational activities. The FIDELIS project's⁹ TTRAM and the MaDSAF A|F are inclusive of any venue¹⁰ where humans and/or machines interact with data and/or metadata, so any organisation(s) with catalogue(s) of digital objects¹¹ are in scope. In this paper we use the term 'repository' broadly and inclusively.

In this paper we use the FIDELIS/TTRAM/MaDSAF term '**digital object**' for any entity composed of data and/or metadata held by a repository. At this level of detail, it aligns closest with the CPP/OAIS¹² term '(Information)' Object. The CPPs focus strongly on the bit-stream and logical (i.e., file/container format, technological dependencies) levels of the digital objects, which are handled in information packages for submission (SIP), dissemination (DIP), and preservation

⁶ EDEN Project <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

⁷ Core Preservation Processes (CPP) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452>

⁸ EDEN CPPs denote an organisation compliant with the CPPs as a 'Trustworthy Digital Archive' (TDA)

⁹ The FIDELIS project is addressing multiple different authorities and criteria related to 'Trustworthy Digital Repositories' (TDA)

¹⁰ The [OSTRAILS Project](#) differentiates 'venue' (Publishing or dissemination channels through which research products are made available[]) from 'data source' ([]where research products are stored, preserved, made discoverable, and accessed. Repositories fulfill both these functions.

¹¹ The concatenation of Organisations(s), Catalogue(s), Objects(s) information allows us to be specific about the scope of any Digital Object Venue Entity (DOVE). L'Hours, H., Parkes, O., Kleemola, M., & Liberante, F. (2026). Trust, Types, Transparency. TIC-TAC-TOE (v01.00). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18640493>

¹² Open Archival Information System (OAIS) <https://ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m3.pdf>

(AIP). We refer to other digital entities that inform repository practice as ‘**information artefacts**’ including any criteria (including policies, standards, procedures) and semantic artefacts such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies.

Repositories that take ongoing responsibility to monitor and update digital objects in order to ensure their long term accessibility and usability despite changes to technology and user needs (*Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}) employ *Format Migration*_{CPP} and/or *Emulation and Rendering Tools*_{CPP}. However, both of these approaches may also be applied by repositories that don’t offer a level of care sufficient to be termed *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}.

The concept of an integrated approach to ‘preservation planning’ was originated by the EOSC Long Term Data Retention Working Group¹³ (LTDR WG). It refers to *integration* both in the sense that all repositories offering all LoRCAP should be included, as well as an integrated approach to sharing comparable information. This approach acknowledges and clarifies similarities and differences across repositories. Repositories benefit from identifying peers with common practice (e.g. through the FIDELIS network) , and depositors, users and funders benefit from clarity that the level of care applied to digital objects aligns with their needs and expectations.

The LTDR has also provided a perspective on *appraisal*_{LTDR}, *reappraisal*_{LTDR}, changes to levels of care, and *disposal*_{CPP} whose terms are identified in the text¹⁴.

Integrated Preservation Planning:

The scope is inclusive of any organisation(s) providing any or all of Retention_{LoRCAP}, Initial Curation_{LoRCAP}, or Active Preservation_{LoRCAP} for any catalogues of digital objects’ data and metadata.

In the text below the CPP policies are underlined.

The MaDSAF provides high-level labels for all repository A|F, including *Preservation*_{A|F}. The TTRAM focus is on repository attributes that inform ‘trust’. The CPPs focus on operational activities for *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}. By applying both of these perspectives, supported by transparent and referenceable information, we can propose a common model for a more integrated approach to preservation planning.

The overall vision is the eventual provision of a TRIPP template that all repositories complete and share to clarify their practice. The scope is inclusive of organisation(s) providing any or all of *Retention*_{LoRCAP}, *Initial Curation*_{LoRCAP}, or *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}, of any catalogues of digital objects’ data and metadata.

The *Mission and Scope*_{A|F} of each repository is defined, including through a Mission Statement.

¹³ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force>

¹⁴ Pending at the time this paper is published.

Organisational Infrastructure: Informing Preservation Planning

The *Legal/Ethical*_{A|F} and *Policy/Standards*_{A|F} environment enforced on, or adopted by a repository informs the framework of *Criteria/Assessment/Improvement*_{A|F} that they comply with. *External Engagement*_{A|F}, including *Community Watch*_{CPP} and technology watch (part of the *Technical Infrastructure*_{A|F}), identifies needs and risk (*Risk Definition and Extraction*_{CPP}, *Risk Mitigation*_{CPP}) that provide further context to preservation planning. A number of these factors will inform the definition of *Rights*_{A|F} (depositor, user, repository, object etc) and the process of *Rights Management*_{CPP} in terms of permissions, prohibitions and obligations¹⁵. This range of internal and external factors inform *Workflows*_{A|F} that define day to day operations and enable *Continuity of Service*_{A|F}.

*Object Management Reporting*_{CPP} provides essential feedback on operational digital object management (see below), but can also input to *Criteria, Assessment Improvement*_{A|F} and potentially *Analysis and Impact*_{A|F}.

Preservation Planning

The criteria adopted and the drivers identified from *External Engagement*_{A|F}, must be sufficiently covered in a Preservation Policy that includes defined *Workflows* for Preservation Action Plans and enables *Continuity of Service*_{A|F}, including an Exit Scenario Plan. All supporting information to be maintained is defined in the Metadata Recording Policy.

A Preservation Policy is informed by all relevant logical and semantic criteria (including *Significant Properties Definition*_{CPP}) used to assess digital objects' data and metadata, as well as any other factors that influence Fitness-for-Use as defined in a Quality Assessment Policy.

For all *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP} repositories, and for many other levels of care, *Format Migration*_{CPP} and *Emulation and Rendering Tools*_{CPP} will be essential to ensuring long term *Access*_{A|F} and *ReUse*_{A|F} of digital objects. Migration and emulation both require an understanding of community and technical perspectives on file formats sufficient to define a File format policy - Preferred formats with an assessment method defined in File format policy - Identification. These policies guide the file format assessments and transformations throughout *Ingest*_{CPP}, as a part of *Deposit Compliance Criteria*_{LoRCAP} (*Deposit & Appraisal*_{A|F}), through *Initial Curation*_{LoRCAP} (*Curation, Quality, Compliance*_{A|F}) and to enable *ReUse*_{A|F} (File format policy - Derivatives). A Packaging Policy defines rules for SIPs, DIPs and AIPs¹⁶.

Digital Object Management Lifecycle

After the *Conceive, Create, Collect*_{A|F} phase of research, digital objects are submitted to repositories for *Deposit and Appraisal*_{A|F}, guided by a Collections Development Policy. If accepted

¹⁵ Terms derived from the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL): <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

¹⁶ Submission, Dissemination and Archival Information Packages. Terms from the [OAIS Reference Model](#).

for *Ingest*_{CPP}, *Metadata Ingest and Management*_{CPP} will take place. Once accepted, the *Retention Policy* is followed through to *ReAppraisal*_{LTD} and, potentially, *Disposal*_{CPP}.

The object may be subject to further *Curation, Quality and Compliance*_{A|F} (*Data Quality Assessment*_{CPP}). This may also include *File Normalisation*_{CPP} to meet repository format requirements.

Digital objects are prepared for *Discovery & Identification*_{A|F} (*Enabling Discovery*_{CPP}, *Identifier Management*_{CPP}: *Identifier creation and Management policy*), *Access*_{A|F} (*Enabling Access*_{CPP}: *Access Policy*). This preparation includes *Creation of Derivative*_{CPP} copies for use by the user community for *ReUse*_{A|F}, (potentially facilitated by *Emulation and Rendering Tools*_{CPP}), and possibly for *Active Preservation*_{LoRCAP}.

Intentional changes to digital objects are recorded as a part of *Provenance and Authenticity*_{A|F} (including *AIP Versioning*_{CPP}: *Versioning Policy*) to ensure traceability .

Diagram 2: CPP Alignment with the Digital Object Management lifecycle activities and functions (A|F)

A number of other *Workflows*_{A|F} may be applied at several points across the digital object lifecycle. These include:

- *Virus Scanning*_{CPP} and *AIP Batch Export*_{CPP} as a part of the repository exit strategy/succession planning (*Continuity of Service*_{A|F})
- *Metadata Extraction*_{CPP}, including for *Metadata Ingest and Management*_{CPP}.
- *File Format Identification*_{CPP} and *File Format Validation*_{CPP}, which are essential for
 - *Deposit & Appraisal*_{A|F} during *Ingest*_{CPP}
 - supporting *Normalisation*_{CPP}
 - ensuring correct formats are provided for DIPs and AIPs through *Format Migration*_{CPP}.

Diagram 3: Workflows deployed multiple times during the digital object management lifecycle.

Storage & Integrity

*Storage & Integrity*_{AlF} includes *Replication*_{CPP} to multiple copies, media (subject to periodic *Refreshment*_{CPP}) and locations. The number of redundant copies are defined in (Storage Management policy - Copies) while the Storage Management Policy - Media specifies technologies and locations.

Every copy is subject to *Integrity Checking*_{CPP} (Storage management policy - Integrity Checking), which depends on each file/object undergoing *Checksum Generation and Recording*_{CPP} (Storage Management Policy - Checksum Algorithms). *Checksum Validation*_{CPP} may be performed after defined events (e.g. a copy or move) or as a part of periodic checks. Integrity failures may be addressed through *Data Corruption Management*_{CPP} that replaces a damaged file with an undamaged copy, or through *File Repair*_{CPP}.

Diagram 4: CPPs Related to Storage & Integrity

MaDSAF to CPP: Overall Alignment

In the diagram below, the mappings between MaDSAF A|F and CPP have been extended to include Policy associations. Green indicates strong, mapping/alignment, orange indicates partial and red indicates no specific mapping or alignment¹⁷.

Diagram 5: MaDSAF to CPP Alignment with additions based in inclusion of CPP Policies

Alignment between MaDSAF and the CPPs terms become clearer with the inclusion of CPP Policies. This includes the explicit or implied inclusion of *Legal & Ethical*_{A|F} and *Policy & Standards*_{A|F} as inputs into *Criteria, Assessment, Improvement*_{A|F}. The relationship with *Mission and Scope*_{A|F} and *Continuity of Service*_{A|F} also becomes stronger.

Repository A|F depend on the *Security*_{A|F} of digital objects as well as a range of technologies incorporating *Technical Infrastructure*_{A|F}. However, CPPs explicitly focus on the operational activities required by digital preservation and do not cover strategic/managerial digital preservation activities or the specifics of information management systems, or secure IT infrastructures. Similarly the CPPs imply a need for, but do not directly reference, *Governance*_{A|F}, *Resources*_{A|F} or *People & Expertise*_{A|F}.

¹⁷ All levels of alignment indicated by colour are also explained in the body of the text.

Below we list the A|F that have not been referenced above. Quoted text is taken from the MaDSAF A|F descriptions and is followed by a brief explanation of 'missing' mappings.

"Identification & Contact: Names, abbreviations and contact details for the organisation to provide reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions."

Essential to understand the organisation, but not specific to preservation.

"3rd Party Dependencies: Identifying and managing third-party organisations, hosts, partners, and other actors that are essential to operations, including the delivery of data or metadata services."

Preservation tools and services may rely on third parties, and these relationships are dependencies for trust assessments, but are not included in the CPPs which are implementation agnostic.

"Conceive, Create, Collect: The stages of the research data lifecycle, before data enters a repository. Working with data or metadata creators and owners can help improve quality and highlight the benefits of curation, preservation and reuse."

Though a repository may request information created in the pre-repository stage, it does not have a direct influence so this lifecycle phase is not addressed by the CPPs.

"Support: Providing guidance and responding to requests from depositors and users around deposit and appraisal, discovery, access and re-use of data and metadata."

Though some trust criteria suggest that a repository should have a support function, this is not a part of the CPPs.

"Release & Publishing: The processes by which the organisation creates, manages, approves, releases, updates and withdraws information artefacts(not deposited digital objects) such as publications, policies, guidelines, and other content related to the repository activities and functions. It includes publishing information that provides evidence for external assessments (see AF24 "Criteria, Assessment, Improvement") and supports external engagement (see AF20 "External Engagement")."

Though managing the release and publishing of information artefacts is essential for transparency and for providing evidence for external assessments, including trust assessments this is not covered by the CPPs, which strictly focus on digital preservation actions.

"Interoperability: The protocols and processes by which people, processes, technologies and digital objects effectively interact with others, both within and across organisational entities."

Ensuring interoperability between digital objects may be a goal of preservation, but this is not a focus of the CPPs.

“Analysis & Impact: The analysis of internal data and external information to verify and demonstrate that the organisation is effectively fulfilling its mission (see AF02 "Mission & Scope").”

Analysis and Impact is more likely to focus on societal impact or delivering on funder expectations. Measures of whether CPP preservation actions are ‘successful’ are primarily aligned with *Criteria, Assessment, Improvement*_{A|F}, though *Object Management Reporting*_{CPP} could inform *Analysis and Impact*_{A|F}.

“Training: Leveraging internal expertise to train data and metadata producers, owners, depositors, and users. Training can cover the entire digital object management lifecycle, from the conception of research to the reuse of data and metadata. It also includes training for internal staff, as well as for peer organisations, partners, and third parties.”

Training from repository staff is a valuable service which can significantly improve the quality of data a repository holds, however, the CPPs focus on activities taken on digital objects starting from the deposit onwards.

“Research & Development (R&D): Projects and other activities outside current operations, routine maintenance and upgrades. This can include new approaches to data, metadata, business processes, technology, security, and research infrastructure.”

R&D is, by definition, not a part of operational preservation practice.

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